

LU-BA Integrating Socio-Economic Aspects of the European Green Deal into Research and Academic Content: A Circular Economy Framework New

Version 2

Description

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Integrating Socio-Economic Aspects of the European Green Deal into Research and Academic Content: A Circular Economy Framework" (LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0046).

This interdisciplinary research project contributes to the advancement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by integrating socio-economic aspects of the European Green Deal into research and academic content, thereby fostering innovation and collaboration towards a CE framework. The main aim of the project is to address key challenges in higher education programs and scientific research related to sustainable development within the Green Deal framework, as well as to create practical tools for students and the business environment that support sustainable development, circular economy and resource efficiency.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

LU-BA grants

Researchers

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Organizations

BA School of Business and Finance, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: LU-BA Integrating Socio-Economic Aspects of the European Green Deal into Research and Academic Content: A Circular Economy Framework New

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

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Grants: [LU-BA grants](#)

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

This interdisciplinary research project contributes to the advancement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by integrating socio-economic aspects of the European Green Deal into research and academic content, thereby fostering innovation and collaboration towards a CE framework. The main aim of the project is to address key challenges in higher education programs and scientific research related to sustainable development within the Green Deal framework, as well as to create practical tools for students and the business environment that support sustainable development, circular economy and resource efficiency.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data collected will be: survey and grey literature assessment results, scripts, interview or workshop/focus-group transcripts or recordings.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

no previously available data on the topic

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

any researcher interested in SDG, green public procurement, circular economy, industrial symbiosis

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Survey methodology description (in Latvian) available here -

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1R55NRWL_qij2yaHSannfMx37EWonwHj7/edit?usp=drive_web&oid=101625450341077186314&rtpof=true and results available here -

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KQ_Y0dxHqfmCqvmgeJCTeGJlQr_Cxgdj/edit?usp=drive_web&oid=101625450341077186314&rtpof=true

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

zenodo.org

Mircosoft Office

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Mircosoft Office

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-16

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

the data remains re-usable until still valid for the researchers

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jekaterina Kuzmina (0000-0003-3318-3782)

Risk prevention will be ensured during the project through the following measures:

1. providing a clear and detailed description of the project;
2. ensuring full transparency for the duration of the project for stakeholders and interests.

The Project Manager will continuously update potential new risks, evaluating their risk and defining the risk treatment measures. The role of the scientific assistant will be to engage in the organization of day-to-day activities, including implementing quality control

measures.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

no additional costs

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

data storage in the university cloud

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Anonymising data

All data is collected and processed in aggregated manner

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